

THE ROLE OF INDEPENDENT INSTITUTIONS IN ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION AND THE FIGHT AGAINST ENVIRONMENTAL CRIME

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Abstract

Beyond the classical separation of powers, which is predominantly linked to the protection and promotion of human freedoms and rights, a large number of institutions that are located between or almost outside Montesquieu's idea have an obligation to act promptly, especially when it comes to the environment and the fight against environmental crime. The evolution of the legal and political order, appreciating its virtues and flaws, has also given rise to a kind of sui generis institutions whose main domain is precisely the protection of rights and freedoms and the promotion of well-being. Although today the modern state can boast of a large number of creations, which are more or less called and ready for action, the constitutional courts and the institutions of the Ombudsman stand out, which, although different, find their connective tissue in the defence of freedoms, rights, and democracy. Especially when the "classical" institutions of the state, which are placed in strong bureaucratic constraints and procedures, cannot respond to the existing crises and challenges, it is necessary for institutions that have the ability for legal interpretation and reasoning (referring to fundamental values and natural law) to react in a timely manner and, to a certain extent, pre-emptively. This paper deals with the role and significance of institutions such as the Constitutional Court and the Ombudsman in the Republic of North Macedonia in the corpus of environmental protection and its advancement. It analyses the most modern actions and modifications of the Ombudsman, who is increasingly and more boldly entering this matter, making it inherent to this position.

Keywords: independent institutions, environmental protection, constitutional court, ombudsman

1. INTRODUCTION

In modern societies, the issue of environmental protection and the fight against environmental crime has quite justifiably become a matter of public interest, human rights, and dignity. Acting outside the classical separation of powers, the constitutional court and

the ombudsman as independent institutions have the role of key actors in the processes of greater integration of environmental rights. Deprived of the strict formalism, rigidity and bureaucracy of traditional authorities (legislative, executive and judicial), they can undoubtedly offer efficient and long-term solutions that are needed by societies at a given moment, using their flexibility and autonomy.

In a historical line, the concept of independent, impartial institutions and moral justice has followed humanity since ancient city-states to the modern, globalized state. The Athenians, at the place called "*The Hill of Ares*", where the god Ares was once tried, founded the Areopagus – an independent judicial institution that should continue the tradition of justice that will this time judge both people and rulers.

Medieval examples with the Forest Charter of 1217 and the ordinances of King Louis XIV show state forms of nature protection, while, somewhat later in the period of the Renaissance and the Enlightenment, we notice a shift in focus towards man and an order that is rational, connecting nature with morality, law and the social contract.

Natural disasters and urban crises of the 19th century formed a legal basis for the concept of environmental rights, examples of the great floods in London and the fires in the USA illustrate how the protection of nature became a public interest, and not just an economic or private issue.

In the 20th century, when at times the separation of powers became outdated and almost out of place and its shortcomings became visible (especially in the protection of human freedoms and rights and issues of mutual control), we witness two processes: **the establishment of constitutional courts** and **ombudsmen**. These are, in fact, chronologically the first independent institutions for the protection of human rights that appear outside of Montesquieu's concept of the separation of powers.

These institutions in the 21st century show that they have a central role in the sphere of environmental protection and the fight against environmental crime. By combining positive law and natural law principles (which, as civilizational developments, are "transmitted" into constitutions and laws), they function as a kind of "*instruments of the conscience*" of the state. The legal and continuous protection of the environment represents a logical and completely natural extension of the already established human rights, while the constitutional courts and the ombudsman become the "*voice*" of nature in the legal systems, striving to prevent environmental damage and protect future generations.

This does not mean that constitutional courts and ombudsmen are similar institutions. They are different in many ways, their role and function are different, but here we single them out and discuss them as two more relevant and most necessary institutions in the legal system (in a situation where there are several independent institutions), especially when the traditional separation of powers is late in anticipating changes. The key difference is certainly in their basic task: constitutional courts are guardians of the constitution and exercise constitutional control (they repeal or annul acts), while the ombudsman is a kind of administrative controller, who investigates and criticizes, but without executive power. This makes both institutions *sui generis*³², outside the legislative, executive and judicial branches. The paper does not compare their competencies (which

³² In Latin, it means "one of a kind". In the context of institutions, it refers to those who do not fit into the classical separation of powers. They have a specific, unique role.

would be “improper” at times), but rather emphasizes their importance and agility in protecting the environment and fighting environmental crime³³.

2. HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT OF THE SEPARATION OF POWERS AND INDEPENDENT INSTITUTIONS

In Europe, during the period of absolutism, where kings were “*God's representatives on earth*” or where, according to the example of Louis XIV in France – “*I am the state*”, tyranny, religious persecution and wars became everyday life. Especially after the English Civil War (1642-1649), the Glorious Revolution (1688), as well as the French Revolution (1789), the need arose for power to be clearly limited by law, and for man to be protected from the state. In order to protect the individual from the arbitrariness of power, which would later form the basis of liberal democracy, John Locke was among the first to outline the limitation of power³⁴. He initially makes a separation of powers: he distinguishes between legislative and executive power. The former enacts laws, while the latter is responsible for their implementation. He also sporadically mentions the judicial power, but it is not tripartite as in Montesquieu. The complete and comprehensive theoretical basis for the concept of separation of powers is provided by Charles Montesquieu, a French philosopher who, especially through his work “*The Spirit of Law*” from 1748, will influence future constitutional processes. He speaks of three powers: legislative, executive and judicial power. For the third, which is not explicitly established by Locke, for example, he will state that it judges according to the laws (courts). These three must be separate, but also balanced, where we have the concept of “*checks and balances*”. Both theorists, one in England and the other in France, have personally experienced violent power and the cruel character of absolutism. Their reflections, guided by what they have witnessed, will form the foundation of modern constitutionalism and human rights.

In 1787, it was in the US Constitution that the previous theoretical concepts would be practically “revived” for the first time. The American founders would refer to Locke and Montesquieu, and the American Constitution would establish for the first time the separation of powers, accompanied by checks and balances, which would serve as a benchmark for modern democracies in Europe. However, the modern state at the turn of the 19th to the 20th century became truly complex, and in the period of increasing state role in the economy, public services and social issues, the separation of powers failed to control all segments. The existing three branches could not provide independent oversight, they closed each other in a circle, which would necessitate the need for new institutions that should fill, neutralize that vacuum and obvious shortcomings.

After the First World War, in Austria (1920) after the collapse of Austria-Hungary, we have the first Constitutional Court built on the theory of pure law of the creator

³³ According to the data of the Basic Criminal Court in Skopje, in the period 2018 to 2024, 29 final verdicts were pronounced for crimes against the environment and nature, of which the most pronounced were suspended sentences in 13 cases, a fine was pronounced in 9 cases, an effective prison sentence was pronounced in 2 verdicts, 1 verdict with a court warning and 1 verdict with a suspended sentence with protective supervision. During this period, 2 proceedings following a filed indictment were stopped, and the indictment was rejected for 1. The picture is similar for other courts in the country.

³⁴ Locke introduced the concept of philosophical legitimation of the separation of powers, according to which - the state exists to protect citizens, while it must be responsible and limited.

Kelsen³⁵. Later, the example of the Second World War illustrates how institutions can be subordinated to one person or one party, with which totalitarian regimes prove that the triadic separation of powers is not enough³⁶.

The Constitutional Court can be cited as the oldest independent institution. This group certainly includes the Ombudsman, who, although initially introduced in 1809, experienced its flowering after the Second World War. After the 1970s, there has been a noticeable trend of establishing various independent anti-corruption and media bodies.

3. THE CONCEPT AND CHARACTER OF INDEPENDENT INSTITUTIONS

Independent institutions appear as a reaction to the period in which the separation of powers in many matters is out of place and has been overcome. In particular, the courts become dependent on the authorities, and serious social and economic problems and challenges faced by the states and societies, the authorities are forced to step aside and form special, specialized institutions as independent mechanisms of control. Constitutional courts, following the example of the Austrian one, take on the role of constitutional control of laws, ombudsmen perform the role of protecting citizens from the administration and government in general, while audit institutions (Sweden, Great Britain, USA), election commissions (the example of India in 1950), anti-corruption bodies (Hong Kong in 1974), etc. also appear. Today, we distinguish a large number of such institutions, in which we clearly perceive the principles of independence, expertise (professionalism), specialization, publicity, etc. Independent institutions for human rights and freedoms are not a new branch of the separation of powers, but a modern extension of the idea of limiting power and the rule of law.

The following is a more detailed explanation of two of the oldest institutions (excluding the legislative, executive and judicial branches) in which their independent character, professionalism and specialization are most evident, and which have a **special, proactive role** in relation to the environment and environmental crime.

3.1 Constitutional Courts

Since their establishment, constitutional courts have been occupied for a long time with issues of “classical” rights, such as civil and political rights (right to life, freedom of speech, etc.). They are focused on what is embedded in the then constitutions of the 18th and 19th centuries. Environmental rights, together with social rights, only developed in the second half of the 20th century, and thus, being constitutionally unregulated, they are practically removed from the domain of constitutional court proceedings.

With the emergence of the first constitutional provisions on environmental protection and the formulation of the right to a healthy environment (SFRY, 1974), a new chapter opens in which the area of the environment becomes eligible for constitutional jurisdiction.

In addition to the need for these rights to be explicitly listed in the constitution (or somehow to be part of the constitutional text), an important moment is also ecological

³⁵ Hans Kelsen (1881–1973) was one of the most influential legal and constitutional theorists of the 20th century. He is best known for his *Reine Rechtslehre* / Pure Theory of Law. According to him, the constitution is the highest norm (*grundnorm*).

³⁶ Especially after the Second World War, many countries will accept the Austrian concept (unlike the American one - where there is no constitutional court, but the Supreme Court has established this jurisdiction itself with a precedent from 1803).

disasters and the increasing visibility of environmental damage. It is precisely the fatal consequences for the environment and nature that will force states and international organizations to pay special attention³⁷. Another point is also the strengthening of the civil sector and awareness of the existence of these problems and the rights related to them.

However, in this section it is of particular importance to point out the character and role of constitutional courts. They are not universal institutions, so their role depends on the constitutional-legal and political order. Their competencies are not “*carved in stone*”, no matter how much there are common characteristics³⁸.

In certain democratic states, they can literally be perceived as the fourth power (this can be understood from the constitutional text of some states, to some extent this solution is also present in the Macedonian constitution of 1991), while in others they are a kind of corrector of the authorities, an “inter-power”, but they can also be marginalized. There are still countries in the world where constitutional judicial control (and constitutional courts in general) is absent, but this is still reserved for absolute monarchies, authoritarian regimes or some micronations. The modern constitutional court of the 20th century is still the first example of an institutionalized, formally independent institution (although earlier forms of control can also be found in the Athenian Areopagus or in the medieval forest courts).

3.1.1. Constitutional Courts as guardians of the Constitution today

A functional constitutional judiciary, as former constitutional judge Šarin (2016) states, is one of the bearers of the democratic rule of law. Constitutional judges are “*neither gods nor servants*”. They are traditionally considered guardians of the constitution, which is their **first obligation**. However, in modern constitutional democracies their role continuously exceeds the control of constitutionality. They are not only the negative legislator as Kelsen believes (according to whom - these courts act negatively, only “erasing” norms from the legal order, and not creating new ones), but also become positive creators thanks to their judicial activism - giving new meaning.

In such a context, judicial activism gains a new, green dimension. When interpreting existing human rights (where, for example, environmental rights do not exist), these courts already include environmental rights, thereby bringing the constitution to life - turning it from a “*dead letter on paper*” into a living, moral instrument. In such a constellation, constitutional courts are not only guardians of the constitution, but they are also guardians of the planet in a legal sense. Such behaviour enters the era of green constitutionalism, and the constitutional court seemingly acts as a mediator between people and nature, advocating a balance between them³⁹.

³⁷ This is also linked to the formation of other concepts, such as environmental security. As authors Koprivnjak and Vidaček (2024) point out, the Cold War period required a more rational and “realpolitik” approach to security, which would include elements that are not only part of the traditional understanding.

³⁸ In the USA, for example, although there is no classic constitutional court, the Supreme Court itself assumes the jurisdiction for constitutional judicial protection and control, which is certainly one of the ways to establish this type of judicial powers.

³⁹ It can be concluded, appreciating the complex relations in society, and those that are yet to develop (digital rights, artificial intelligence, environmental rights, etc.), that we are talking about a “*functional spillover*”, where all institutions act outside their domain. Especially if we talk about the constitutional court and the ombudsman, then we see the positive effects in the rapid response (especially in environmental crime, for

Constitutional courts, as Đurić (2012) states, can also be an important actor in the process of European integration, which implies, among other things, the integration of the national order into the European one.

3.2 Ombudsman

The emergence of the ombudsman opens a new chapter in the relations between those who govern and those who are governed, between the state and citizens, between public servants and the public. The ombudsman appears in a dual role. He is equally an instrument for the protection of human rights and a unique mechanism for democratic control over the administration (Aviani, 1999, p. 67).

The authors Vidaček and Ristovska (2024) state that the ombudsman, as a “*megaphone*”, has the task of revealing legal problems and inappropriate actions of the administration and, with the help of professional and legal interventions, to try to restore justice and equality in the everyday system of legal relations. However, it is wrong to idealize this function and attribute to it some “*super-legal*” characteristics.

The Ombudsman, according to Akimovska Maletić and Vidaček (2025), as an informal, additional, non-repressive and non-judicial mechanism for the protection of human rights and freedoms, protects citizens from bad governance. Based on the mandate of the Ombudsman institutions, they have a significant role in the advancement and protection of human rights and fundamental freedoms, in promoting good governance and respect for the rule of law. The authors also recall the attempt from 1974, with the Yugoslav constitutional solution, to establish a “*public ombudsman of self-government*”, which is a kind of body to what is clearly called an ombudsman today.

Over time, specialized ombudsmen have also been established. They have been established for the environment, children, information, minorities, languages, etc. Appreciating that the world is moving towards specialized institutions, which as a process does not bypass the ombudsman, in a text from 2008, Professor Iskra Maletić Akimovska asks the question - *does Macedonia need an environmental ombudsman?* That, both then and today, would certainly yield better results in environmental protection by the Ombudsman.

4. THE INFLUENCE OF INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS

International law, after 1945, has been adopting new standards for human rights as a result of the need for people to be protected not only from the state, but also from the abuse of power and the neglect of public goods (including nature and the environment). The UN has approached the issue of the environment indirectly, and this is derived from the right to life, health, etc. Especially in the 1970s, the UN recommended the establishment of specialized institutions for human rights (and later for environmental protection). This gradually led to the ombudsman gaining powers in environmental issues, and constitutional courts having the legitimacy to protect the “new” rights.

example), the strengthening of moral interest and the enabling of synchronization of different policies and rights. Especially in the case of constitutional courts, their intention for a gap-filling function is noticeable.

4.1 Stockholm Declaration

In 1972, the Stockholm Declaration for the first time put the environment in relation to global challenges and human freedoms and rights. This declaration has 26 principles that form the future international environmental law.

According to Ristovska, Akimovska Maletić and Vidaček (2025), the declaration introduces the concept of the right to a clean environment, although it does not directly recognize it. It first formulates the right to the environment (of course not as clearly as it would be in the 1974 Constitution of the SFRY), advocates the rational use of natural resources and stipulates the principle of “no harm”, which would later become widely accepted in international law. Although the declaration is not legally binding, it has played a crucial role when it comes to environmental protection. It will pave the way for a new type of constitutionalism - titled “ecological” or “green” constitutionalism, which means integrating as many provisions for environmental protection as possible and clearly establishing the right to the environment. According to Vidaček and Ristovska (2025), the right to the environment is a vestibule of green constitutionalism.

Somewhat later, even constitutional courts begin to refer to the Stockholm Declaration. This is especially evident in the Indian Supreme Court, which, as one of the most active in environmental protection, has referred to the declaration in several judgments since the 1980s. The court in the case *Rural Litigation and Entitlement Kendra v. State of U.P.* (1985–1986) banned the exploitation of limestone in the Himalayas, because it threatened forests and watercourses. This is considered the first environmental decision in India in which the court directly mentioned the Stockholm Declaration, which as an international treaty obliges states to protect nature.

The court in India remained known for its activism in the following decades. For example, in a case from 1996, the court cited the Stockholm Declaration and the Rio Declaration (1992) and stated that they were also binding on India. The Supreme Court has ruled that the “precautionary principle”, the “polluter pays” principle and sustainable development are fundamental and inseparable from Indian national law. In doing so, it has incorporated the fundamental principles into its order. The court “takes” the Stockholm Convention as “soft law” and interprets constitutional norms through it. Through such judicial activism, this institution also becomes a “positive legislator” when it comes to environmental cases. This approach will also inspire courts in the Philippines, Bangladesh and Pakistan.

4.2 Paris Principles (1993)

The Paris Principles were adopted by UN General Assembly resolution 48/134 of 1993 (and were previously adopted in Paris in 1991). Their aim is to define minimum standards for the independence, mandate and operation of national human rights institutions (known as NHRIs)⁴⁰. They prescribe 6 key criteria. First, there must be a broad mandate in relation to universal human rights (this certainly includes “environmental” rights). Second, they must be independent of government - both organizationally and financially. Third, their composition is required to reflect social and professional pluralism. Furthermore, financial autonomy of these institutions is advocated. As a penultimate, these

⁴⁰ In this paper, we use the term independent institutions as a broader, more inclusive term than the abbreviation NHRI. The Ombudsman is, for example, a classic NHRI institution, while the constitutional court has a specific position in the entire legal system.

principles require the possibility of these institutions to investigate, recommend measures and advise. The last principle is the need for active international cooperation (Council of Europe, UN, etc.).

5. “FUNCTIONAL SPILLOVER” EFFECT

In the 21st century, when the traditional separation of powers is no longer absolute, we can increasingly speak of the spillover effect. It can be concluded, appreciating the complex relations in society, and those that are yet to develop (digital rights, artificial intelligence, environmental rights, etc.), that we are talking about a “*functional spillover*”, where all institutions act outside their domain. Especially if we talk about the constitutional court and the ombudsman, then we see the positive effects in the rapid response (especially in environmental crime, for example), the strengthening of moral interest and the enabling of synchronization of different policies and rights. Especially in the case of constitutional courts, their intention for a gap-filling function is noticeable.

No matter how positive we evaluate the activity of these two categories of independent institutions, we still need to foresee the danger that comes from this. These are actually side effects⁴¹, because behind these sometimes glorified institutions, there is still a human being, *errare humanum est*. It can be concluded that we distinguish among them preventive, reactive, educational, symbolic (moral) and other functions.

6. ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION IN THE REPUBLIC OF NORTH MACEDONIA

In the Republic of North Macedonia, “the regulation and humanization of space and the protection and improvement of the environment and nature” are part of the fundamental values, along with “respect for the generally accepted norms of international law” (stipulated in Article 8). In Article 43, the Macedonian Constitution establishes that “Every person has the right to a healthy environment. Everyone is obliged to improve and protect the environment and nature. The Republic provides conditions for the exercise of the right of citizens to a healthy environment”. This solution is similar to the solution of 1974, only that the then “social community” has now been replaced by “republic”. In this way, the constitution first gives an individual dimension (as a subjective right), and then a collective dimension (collective right) representing the environment as a *res communis omnium* – a public good that at the same time belongs to no one, and is common to all. It is a subjective - collective right, because the deprivation of any property would devastate the other moment. For the state, however, there is both an active and passive obligation. Such a constitutional framework⁴², further supplemented by the multitude of laws, creates an excellent basis for the actions of the constitutional court and the ombudsman.

⁴¹ Constitutional courts, and with them the Ombudsman, can easily play with their “extended” competencies, and consciously or unconsciously lead to a conflict of competencies. Such proactive actions (previously explained as “spillover”) can also lead to parallel decisions and recommendations, which would seriously burden the legal system and stability (example: the Ombudsman and the government may have different recommendations regarding forest management). In a situation of excessive, extensive understanding of competencies, these institutions can be defamed as those who want to subjugate democratic processes and declare themselves “superpowers” (when the court repeals/annuls an act due to environmental damage, and the other side claims that democratic principles are being violated).

⁴² With Amendment XVII, environmental protection also becomes an issue of local importance.

6.1 Constitutional Court of the Republic of North Macedonia

The constitutional judiciary in Macedonia began operating in 1964, and was first established with the Constitution of the Socialist Republic of Macedonia of 1963. The right to the environment is established in the 1974 constitutions of the Socialist Federal Republic of Yugoslavia and the Socialist Republic of Macedonia.

As can be seen from a statement by the former President of the Constitutional Court, Dobrila Kacarska from 2022⁴³, what is most often the case when the Court determines that there is a violation is in cases in which the constitutionality and legality of decisions on the adoption of urban plans are assessed. She then recalled the repeal of the Decision on Amendments and Supplements to the Urban Plan outside the Settlement Ski Centre Vodno – Block 3, Municipality of Karpoš from 2015 (U.br.36/2021), where a violation of constitutional and legal norms was found by the Municipality, which did not publish on its website the decisions on non-implementation, i.e. on conducting a strategic assessment of the impact of the planning document on the environment, although it has a legal obligation.

In 2000, for example, the Constitutional Court repealed an article from the Law on Amendments to the Law on Catering and Tourism Activities (112/2000-0-0) and annulled a paragraph that reads: “unless otherwise determined by the detailed urban plan”. Also, in 2005, the Constitutional Court (U.br.233/2005-1) repealed Article 85, paragraph 3, in the section on “compensation of costs” of the Law on Environment. Perhaps more interesting is the example of the repeal of the Decision (U.br.6/2013-1) on the adoption of an urban plan outside a populated area - part of the tourist complex "Sveti Stefan" in the Municipality of Ohrid, adopted by the Council of the Municipality of Ohrid in 2012. The court determined that this decision called into question the principle of the rule of law and the regulation and humanization of space and the protection and promotion of the environment and nature, as contrary to Article 8 paragraph 1 lines 3 and 10 of the Constitution, but also contrary to the provisions of the Law on Spatial and Urban Planning.

However, no matter how much it is accepted that the Constitutional Court has acted in the area of the environment, creating a solid practice, it is not too much along the lines of “living constitutionality” or judicial activism. It can be concluded that the Constitutional Court was not too brave in giving some kind of more extensive interpretation. “Revolutionary” actions that would give a different meaning to the environment are missing.

However, we can single out one decision from 2019 (U.br.130/2018), in which the Constitutional Court repealed provisions of the Law on Drinking Water Supply and Urban Wastewater Disposal, thus determining that it is unconstitutional to interrupt the supply of drinking water when the user does not fulfil the payment obligation. In the explanation, the Constitutional Court refers to the fundamental values, and among other things determines that according to Article 10, paragraph 1 of the Constitution, human life is inviolable. In this case, registered as U.br.130/2018 of 08.05.2019, we see that the Macedonian court is leaving its “comfort zone” and slightly entering the domain of “green constitutionalism”, appreciating that the right to water is closely correlated with the right to the environment and the fight against environmental crime (the environment also includes the water segment).

⁴³ The speech of the former President of the Constitutional Court entitled “To introduce a constitutional complaint, the right of citizens to a healthy environment is limited before the Constitutional Court” is available on the court's website. More at: www.ustavensud.mk/archives/21809

As even the constitutional judges themselves point out to some extent, at least those who are proponents of the “constitutional appeal” (which we do not know, or at least it is limited only to the rights and freedoms provided for in Article 110, paragraph 3), such a cross-section is to some extent a result of the non-coverage of the right to environment under the mechanism of requesting protection of freedoms and rights. It can be appreciated that, however, the Supreme Court, through a principled legal opinion⁴⁴ from 2024, which obliged the state to provide clean air and a healthy environment, has taken primacy before the Constitutional Court. Such “bolder” decisions, however, have not been observed at the Constitutional Court.

6.2 Ombudsman in the Republic of North Macedonia

The institution was established by the constitution in 1991. The institution began operating in 1997 (when the first law was adopted), and currently this matter is regulated by the new Law on the Ombudsman of 2003 ("Official Gazette of the Republic of Macedonia" No. 60/03 of 22.09.2003).

The Ombudsman is a recognized institution in the field of protection, promotion and advancement of human freedoms and rights. The large annual number of complaints from citizens confirms this position. However, the same cannot be said for the field of the environment.

In the period of 6 years (2019-2024), the Ombudsman reported⁴⁵ a total of 110 complaints through its reports, which is an exceptionally low number compared to other areas covered by the Ombudsman. If the average value is calculated, then it amounts to 18.3 complaints per year, which is certainly low. In addition, it is worth noting the share of complaints in the field of the environment in relation to the total number of complaints submitted. In 2019, the share was 0.52%, a decrease was recorded the following year and amounted to 0.41%, while in 2021 a share of 0.45% was recorded. In 2022, the share was 0.53 (which shows an increasing trend), which is also reflected in 2023 with a share of 0.75%. The largest share, which represents the only share above 1%, is the share from the last year, which amounted to 1.18%.

Complaints addressed to the Ombudsman are largely considered the dominant “input” in terms of his actions. Complaints serve as a source of information on possible irregularities, violations and restrictions of rights and freedoms, as well as the presence of maladministration. Based on such complaints, the institution initiates investigations, analyses, conducts direct inspections, provides recommendations and remarks, and in

⁴⁴ Following an initiative to establish a principled position submitted by the Law Firm "Godžo, Kičeev and Novakovski", the Supreme Court on 08.10.2024 discussed at a session whether the state is responsible for Macedonian citizens breathing polluted air, i.e. to what extent the state provides conditions for the realization of the right of citizens to a healthy environment, in accordance with the legally established duties and competencies in the field of the environment. The position of the Macedonian Supreme Court is that "in the realization of the rights to a healthy environment, the provisions of the Law on Administrative Disputes are applied, which provide judicial protection from illegal acts and actions (or failed actions) that violate the constitutionally guaranteed rights and freedoms of man and citizen, when that specific judicial protection is not provided for by the Constitution and other laws". Hence, the state is obliged to provide a healthy environment, and failure to take action is a violation of the rights of citizens.

⁴⁵ The Ombudsman's reports are available on the institution's official website. More at: www.ombudsman.mk

certain situations initiates changes to the legal regulations. Therefore, we observe complaints as an initial mechanism through which the Ombudsman is directed at specific problems.

The environment also has a very low share when it comes to cases initiated on its own initiative. It can be concluded that the Ombudsman initiates cases on its own initiative on an annual basis, but the environment is outside the dominant areas. There are years in which the Ombudsman did not initiate a single case related to the environment.

From media articles and appearances by representatives of the institution, it can be noted that in recent years the Ombudsman has been involved in a more active fight for environmental protection and environmental justice. A certain period of time is needed for his engagement to take effect.

The conclusion is that despite the acute but persistent environmental problems (air, soil, water pollution, problems with waste management and disposal, endangerment of flora and fauna...) citizens use the Ombudsman mechanism to a low extent. This can be attributed to some extent to the practice so far according to which the Ombudsman has built a somewhat greater authority in the areas of children's rights, persons with disabilities, consumer rights, health care, penal and correctional and educational-correctional homes, etc. On the other hand, it is worth highlighting the observation that although the Ombudsman provides a somewhat broader scope using the formulation "environment" (and not only environmental law), it can be noted from the cases handled that they are predominantly of a personal nature, related to several categories (air, water, soil, noise). It is not excluded that the Ombudsman will show a proactive stance where legal and by-laws are adopted contrary to the fundamental values of the constitutional order and environmental law. The Ombudsman can on many occasions ascertain a violation of the environment and actions contrary to these provisions.

The Ombudsman has the opportunity to act also in situations where some derived rights are obstructed, which, although not exhaustively listed, arise from the very essence and nature of the provisions, i.e. when such a ratio legis requires. Through his correct legal interpretation (when applying a broader and holistic interpretation of the law), he can establish such a legal practice that in the future, by means of (first) legal precedent, will provide even broader guarantees and respect for rights.

The environment (as a social and natural term, not necessarily a legal or security one) and environmental law, due to their polyvalent character, have a serious potential to develop rights and practices that the legal system has not yet accepted (which are not initially in contradiction to it). Therefore, it is really interesting to see the Ombudsman's actions appreciating its inherence with human freedoms and rights and democracy.

Given that the Ombudsman in this area shows weaker performance (compared to other "traditional" areas for him), there is an undoubted period of popularization and promotion of this institution in the field of the environment. In fact, here we have a strengthening of awareness through campaigns and activities on two issues, firstly on the issue of the environment and environmental law (which is under threat), and secondly on the Ombudsman as its protector (and the possibility of submitting complaints). However, the lack of initiative by the Ombudsman and other independent institutions may lead to seeking justice in Strasbourg⁴⁶ or to resort to other legal mechanisms⁴⁷ which have been unknown so far.

⁴⁶ There are a large number of applications submitted by Macedonian citizens to the Court of Human Rights in Strasbourg concerning the right to a healthy environment, on which no decisions

CONCLUSION

A state that protects the environment is not possible without independent and efficient institutions. In this millennium, it is noticeable how states are transforming into what the theory calls the “*ecological state*”, where environmental protection is not just a declaration, nor a political priority, but a clear constitutional obligation that projects a new, deconstructed system. In such a situation, constitutional courts and ombudsmen (as the first, oldest independent institutions outside the three branches of government) are the guardians of the new order that increasingly integrates provisions on environmental law, sustainable development, climate change and the rights of future generations.

Constitutional courts and ombudsmen act in a polyvalent manner, as legal, moral and educational mechanisms that stand as a bulwark against attacks on nature, creating an additional institutional framework for environmental protection and the fight against environmental crime. However, such a fight is largely conditioned by the activity of citizens. They must “feed” these institutions with information, complaints and lawsuits, because these institutions still predominantly work on the principle of “inputs”.

Citizens around the world are still largely oriented towards constitutional courts and ombudsmen, before whom they present their demands for the protection of both their rights and the rights of nature and future generations. Climate lawsuits are becoming a reality.

Especially in constitutional courts, the transition from a positivist to a natural-legal and ecological paradigm has been observed, linking the environment directly with man, his dignity, well-being, health.

However, this is not the case with the Republic of North Macedonia. In the practice of the Constitutional Court so far, it is noticeable that it has acted in environmental cases, but they are predominantly related to detailed urban plans or other legal/sub-legal acts. Apart from the decision related to the right to water, the court has not recorded any “more revolutionary” actions, which places it in the group of more conservative constitutional courts (which is not the case with the American, Indian or other).

Although the Ombudsman has been mentioning the environment and surroundings since its early years, it has also recorded “more modest” actions, which are mainly outside its dominant preoccupation.

After analysing the actions of both institutions in the country, it can be emphasized that strengthened constitutional control, accompanied by an expanded ombudsman mandate, as well as the possible establishment of a special department within the ombudsman, will contribute to more efficient protection of environmental rights.

However, both institutions are showing significant shifts and opportunities for change in the existing paradigm. Their louder appeals and speeches, in which they at least declaratively join the fight for environmental and climate justice, provide rational space for belief in their more extensive and revolutionary approach.

have yet been made. These decisions are of importance for further court proceedings that would be conducted in the Republic of North Macedonia, as well as the manner and mechanisms for taking action by the state, state and private entities for a healthy environment as a fundamental human right.

⁴⁷ The State Attorney's Office of the Republic of North Macedonia has filed a civil case in which the state is being sued over the right to clean air, it is in court proceedings and has not yet been legally concluded.

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